

The Historical Roots of the Image of Timurid Princesses

Djalilova Durdona Zairkhodja qizi

A basic doctoral student at the Alisher Navoi University of the Uzbek Language and Literature

Abstract. *This article discusses the place of the glorious Great Timur of Turan and Timurid princesses in historical works and fiction. Interesting information is provided about the position of Timurid princesses in the Timurid empire. The article uses the necessary literature.*

Key words: *historical novel, princess, historical figure, image, sahibkiran, princes, historical reality, historical truth.*

The artistic image is the main feature of art. Art reflects reality with the help of an artistic image (image). The concepts of art and artistic image complement, enrich, and explain each other. Art is fully manifested through the medium of artistic image. The artistic image is an important "cell" of art, without which art does not exist, the artistic image determines the main feature of art. Therefore, the artistic image is the main stage in revealing the nature of art.

Looking back at history, we can see that Eastern women made a significant contribution to the management of state institutions, the promotion of science, culture, art, and spirituality, and there is a lot of historical information about their wisdom and ingenuity, feminine chastity and potential, courage and bravery. Not only in the East, but in all countries familiar to us, women have grown up as compassionate rulers, wise advisers, accomplished sages, brilliant scholars, orators, poets, and brilliant art critics. For example, the ruler of the Massagetae, Tomaris, the ruler of ancient Palmyra, Zinovia, the Spanish Queen Isabella, the Armenian Queen Tamar were all accomplished political rulers of their time. There are many examples of such intelligent, enterprising, and wise women during the reign of Temur and the Temurids.¹

In particular, in the science of history, studying the history of our ancestors, giving them a correct and impartial assessment, and restoring our national values on this basis has reached a new level in the field of history in the renewed Uzbekistan. After all, as our President Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted: "We have a great history worthy of admiration. We have great ancestors worthy of admiration."² Amir Temur, a great commander and patron of science, who built a great empire in his time and took a worthy place in Uzbek statehood and world history, is a great commander. The history of Amir Temur and the Timurid era attracts the attention of many researchers as a universally recognized period in the development of not only our country, but also world civilization. The services of the chief of the palace queens, Saraymulkhanim, in strengthening and managing the state institutions of Amir Temur, in the economic, economic, and cultural upliftment and civilization of the country, in raising the Timurid princes as masters of their time and perfect people were limitless. She stood out from other queens with her extraordinary beauty, charming charm, loyalty, wisdom, and responsiveness. That is why Saraymulkhanim earned the sincere respect and loyalty of Amir Temur. Later, during the reign of Amir Temur, the traditions of sincere respect and favor for intelligent, wise women were

¹ Fayziev T. Temurian princesses. - Tashkent, 1994. - P.3

² From the speech of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the meeting with the creative and intellectual representatives of Uzbekistan // Xalq so'zi 2017-yil 4-yil August).

preserved during the reign of the Timurids. The Timurid princess Gulbadanbegim, who became famous as a historian, is the author of the work "Humoyunnoma", which combines the history, geography, and ethnography of Movorunnahr, Khorasan, and India in the 15th century. Referring to this work, Gulbadanbegim is a scholar who responsibly continued the historiography developed by such great scholars as Sharafiddin Ali Yazdi, Abdurazzaq Samarkandi, Ibn Arabshah, Mirkhand, and Khandamir in Movorunnahr and Khorasan in the 15th century. We can cite many such examples here. In order to further develop the national pride and patriotism of the citizens of Uzbekistan and the younger generation, 1996 was declared the "Year of Amir Timur"³. This increased interest in the history of Timur and the Timurids. The activities of the Timurid princesses are covered on the basis of historical and scientific sources. Information about the role of women during the era of Timur and the Timurids can be found in Nizamuddin Shami's "Zafarnama", Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi's "Zafarnama", Ibn Arabshah's (1389-1450) "Ajoyib ul-maqdur fi akhbori Taimur" (The miracles of fate in the news about Timur), Hafiz Abro's "Zubdat ut-tavarikh Baysunguri", Kamoliddin Abdurazzoq Samarqandi's (1413-1482) "Matlai Sa'dayn va majmai bahrayn" ("The place where the two blessed stars rise and meet the two seas"), Fasih Khawafi's (born in 1375)⁴ "Mujmal-I Fasihiy", Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's (1433-1530) "Boburnama", Ghiyosiddin Muhammad Khandamir's (1475-1535) "Habib us-siyar fi akhbori "Afrod ul-Bashar" ("Biographies of Friends in Human Messages"), Gulbadanbegim's (1523-1603) "Humayunnama", Abulfazl Allami's (1551-1602) "Akbarnama", the fourth ruler of the Babur dynasty, Jahongirshah (1569-1627) "Jahongirnama" ("Jahongir's Regulations"), Mirza Alaiddin Adoul Mulk at-Tavji's "Shahjahonnama", Hakimkhan Tora's "Muntahab ut-tavorikh", "Tazkirat ul-khavotun" ("Women's Tazkir") and "Mashahirunniswan" (Famous Women) are reflected in historical sources such as Examples of works written after the independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan include the historical scientific and popular works of B. Akhmedov, A. Akhmedov, A. Askarov, A. Orinbayev, Kh. Ziyoyev, Azamat Ziyoyev, Kh. Bobobekov, T. Fayziyev, R. Shamsutdinov, P. Ravshanov, U. Uvatov, Sh. Karimov, O. Buriyev. Foreign historians have also written works about the Timurid era. These include the drama "Temur the Great" by Christopher Marlowe (1564-1593), the works of Edward Gibbon (1737-1794), the Austrian Hammer-Purgstall (1774-1856), the German Friedrich Schlosser (1176-1861), and Max Muller (1823-1900). In addition, if we give an example from the work of the French historian Rene Grussé, "The Empire of the Desert", he points out that "the historians of the Timurids try to trace his lineage to one of Genghis Khan's associates and even to one of the Genghisids. In fact, he was not a Mongol at all, he was a Turk."⁵ Indeed, he is a Turkish emir. He is a child of Turkestan, this is a truth that does not require proof. To feel that this is true, one should pay attention to the following situation. In particular, the issue of the role of women in the life of Amir Temur and his descendants is covered in the works of Ruy Gonzalez de Clavijo. Clavijo, while giving information about the daughter of one of the rulers of Khorezm, the granddaughter of the Golden Horde Khan Uzbek Khan, whose real name was Sevinch Beka, states that she was first the wife of Amir Temur's eldest son Jahongir, and after his death she was given to the third son of the sahibkiran, Miranshah. In particular, he describes the following about Khanzoda Begim. The ambassadors were led inside, and before we visited the place where Khanzoda (begim) was sitting, he invited the ambassadors to sit on the platform under the umbrella in front of him. Khanzoda Begim and the women in his presence were sitting under the umbrella in front of the door of the large tent. Today he was holding a wedding for one of his relatives. Begim was described as a pale-faced woman of about forty years of age.⁶ Klaviho writes the following about Saraymulkhanim: "After all the guests had taken their seats and were seated, his eldest wife Kano (Saraymulkhanim), who was to be present at the wedding, came out of one of the saropards near the palace. The lady was dressed like this: A long and wide sleeveless red silk dress with a hem embroidered with beads, reaching down to the floor, narrowed at the waist and widened towards the hem. About fifteen women carried the hem of the dress. To protect the lady from the sun, so much white upa was applied to her face that her face looked like white paper. All noble women who went on a trip in winter and summer applied such oily upa to their faces. The lady's face is

³ Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. PF-1333 dated 26.12.1995.

⁴ Fayziev T. Timurid princesses.-Tashkent, 1994. -P.4

⁵ Amir Temur in world history. -Tashkent., 1996.-P. 40

⁶ Rui Gonzalez de Clavijo. Diary of a trip to Samarkand-Amir Temur's palace (1403-1406 years).-Tashkent,2010.-P.172.

covered with a thin white cloth, and on her head is a high, red headdress, similar to a helmet worn only in battle. One end of it falls on the lady's shoulder. Many large, single pearls, rubies, turquoise, and other various precious stones are set on that red helmet. The part of the headdress that still falls on the shoulder is sewn with beads, and a beautiful gold leaf decorated with precious stones and large pearls is attached to it. It has been noted that the lady's jet black hair fell on her shoulders. Information about the Timurid queens can also be found in the work "Baburnama" by Zahiriddin Muhammad Baburshah (1483-1530). Zahiriddin Muhammad Babur's "Baburnama" is also notable as a historical and literary source because it provides information about many historical figures, people of literature and art, people of religion, kings and princes, beks, emirs and umaros. 357 historical figures from Transoxiana are people of various categories. In particular, 5 are emirs and emirs; 20 are kings and princes; 42 are princesses and royal daughters; 52 are umaros, military leaders and beks; 21 are religious and mystical people; 30 are scientists and writers; 187 are various people - soldiers, farmers, people of art, craftsmen, slaves, and yogis.⁷ Amir Temur and Temur the period is considered a period of awakening in the history of our country. The development of science and culture is embodied not only by the princes of Temurid, but also by the work of the queens. Saraymulk-Khonim is a Timurid queen who went down in history under the name of a faithful wife, a great queen, and a patroness of science. A person who was able to show how great and powerful a woman is in the conditions of the Middle Ages. Gavharshodbegim has her own place among the Timurid queens. History gives different assessments of this woman. We can see that the political situation had a very strong influence on Gavharshodbegim's activities, and in the person of this woman, who was the respected mother of Mirzo Ulugbek, who introduced the culture of Movorunnahr to the world, which left a great mark in history, great courage and unique abilities in state management. It is difficult to imagine the almost forty-year activity of Shahrukh, who united Movarounnahr, Khorasan, and Iran under one center, without Gavharshad Begum. In conclusion, we can see that in our ancient history there were many intelligent queens of their time, and that the service of the Timurid queens in the strength of the foundation of Amir Temur and the Timurid state and its prosperity was incomparable.

List of used literature:

1. From the speech of President Shavkat Mirziyoyev at the meeting with the creative intellectuals and intellectuals of Uzbekistan // *Khalkso'zi*, August 4, 2017).
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, No. PF-1333 dated 26.12.1995.
3. Abdullayeva M. Comparative analysis of the art of literary and historical works.-Tashkent, 2020 P.49
4. Amir Temur in world history. -Tashkent., 1996.-P. 40
5. Ryuy Gonzales de Clavijo. Diary of a trip to Samarkand-Amir Temur's palace (1403-1406 years).- Tashkent,2010.-P.172.
6. Fayziev T. Temur princesses.-Tashkent,1994. –P.3

⁷ Abdullayeva M. Comparative analysis of the art of literary and historical works. - Tashkent, 2020 P.49